

New ISA features and low-level effect handler implementations

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April 15, 2026

Abstract

Memory handling errors and control flow manipulation have been a huge source of problems in computer systems recently, often necessitating rapid update cycles or expensive software mitigation. New features have been added over time to instruction set architectures to provide effective and more efficient protection. These enforce proper control flow and memory usage, and can provide precise and timely fault information on failures. However, these are designed with a standard C-like execution model in mind and software which deviates from this may require adaption to be compatible with new features while retaining their benefits. Here we report on the adaptations required for low-level effect handler libraries which extend standard C execution with non-local control flow and suspended computations.

There is an ongoing trend to provide better memory protection in hardware, especially where executable code is concerned. For example, an early intervention was to prevent execution from writable memory locations to make it more difficult to run data supplied as input as if it were code. However, this required changes to some language implementations that generate machine code dynamically, such as just-in-time compilers.

Here, we consider the impacts of several new architectural features on the control-flow features at the heart of effect handler implementations for low-level languages. We focus on two implementations for C: *libmprompt* [12], which builds effect handlers on top of a library for multi-prompt delimited control, and uses virtual memory to provide light-weight stacks; and *libseff* [2] which uses coroutines. Both of these use assembly code to provide stack switching.

For the instruction set, we base our work on the Arm AArch64 architecture. Other ISAs have similar features, either in deployment or developed to some extent, but we have the greatest familiarity with Arm and access to hardware for the experimental Morello CHERI architecture. We consider four new features in detail:

Branch Target Identification which limits dynamic branch targets to special ‘landing pad’ instructions,

Pointer Authentication Codes which add a small cryptographic signature to the pointer for integrity, forgery resistance, and to prevent the confusion of data and instruction pointers,

Guarded Control Stacks maintain a shadow stack of return pointers, enforcing the use of the top value at each `ret` instruction, and

CHERI hardware capabilities which extend pointers with bounds and permission metadata, plus an extra bit of memory to prevent tampering.

We also briefly consider a few other extensions that we have less practical experience of.

In the present work our goal is to examine compatibility with each feature, rather than to evaluate the security implications, or potential security improvements.

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The main adaptations of software are available online from the repositories below:

Repository	Feature	branch / tag
https://github.com/epoch-project/libmprompt	Branch target identification	<code>bti</code>
	Pointer authentication	<code>arm-pac</code>
	CHERI (Arm Morello)	<code>morello</code>
https://github.com/epoch-project/libseff	Branch target identification	<code>bti</code>
	Pointer authentication	<code>pac</code>
	CHERI (Arm Morello)	<code>morello</code>

Acknowledgements The work described here is part of the project *EPOCH: Effectful Programming on Capability Hardware* funded by the Huawei-Edinburgh Joint Lab at the University of Edinburgh, School of Informatics. We would also like to thank Keith Miller and Marcus Plutowski of Apple for closely related discussions about WebAssembly implementation.

1 Branch Target Identification

Branch Target Identification (BTI) requires indirect branches (that is, where the target is chosen at runtime) to reach a special landing pad instruction. The intent is to prevent some *jump-oriented programming* attacks which corrupt the target address to run some arbitrary piece of code in the program chosen by the attacker [6, Jump-oriented programming]. They can also reduce speculative execution attacks by limiting the potential target addresses in the same way. The landing pad instructions also indicate whether they are allowed to be reached by a function call, local control flow, or both. Function returns do not require a landing pad, but their return addresses can be protected by Guarded Control Stacks, see Section 3.

For compatibility with older compiled code, a *note* annotation in object files indicates when binary code has been built with BTI support, and the kernel only enables BTI checking when the whole executable supports it. The landing pad instructions are allocated as *hint* instructions, which is a range of opcodes that behave as no-operation instructions in earlier versions of the architecture. This allows BTI supporting code to be run on pre-BTI processors without alteration.

The Zicflip RISC-V extension provides a similar feature, with a more elaborate labelling feature instead of the call, jump, or both indicator. The Indirect Branch Tracking in the Intel architecture’s Control-Flow Enforcement Technology [11, Ch. 18] also provides landing pads, but does not have any labelling.

1.1 Adaption

To make our effect handler libraries work with BTI, we must ensure every location that might be called by an indirect branch has a landing pad instruction, and add the note to indicate that we support BTI.

In `libmprompt`’s assembly the only branch targets are the functions themselves, and we only need to add the landing pads to support calls to them through function pointers. Indeed, if they are left out then the test cases still run — this indicates a minor hazard: missing landing pads may not be detected in testing.

However, we also need to consider locations that the assembly code might branch to. For `libmprompt`, the only indirect branch is to the target function to be called after switching to a fresh stack, which the compiler will already provide with a suitable landing pad. The other functions use return instructions, which do not require BTI. However, it may be desirable to change these to branches to improve branch prediction; for example, `glibc`’s `longjmp` function has a comment that they use a branch for exactly this reason. Possible targets for these branches would then need landing pads. Fortunately, compilers already have a mechanism for this — functions like `setjmp` can be annotated with the `returns_twice` attribute. The corresponding `libmprompt` function already had this, and we confirmed that these are present in the generated code.

The port of libseff was largely similar, except that the function to exit a coroutine used a jump to return and the caller might not have a landing pad. This was fixed by changing it to a return instruction. This may cause similar branch prediction issues, but they would only occur at the end of coroutines, which are relatively infrequent.

An alternative fix would be to annotate the function so that compilers generate a landing pad after calls. GCC supports an `indirect_return` attribute for this. Currently, the clang compiler only supports the `returns_twice` attribute used for `setjmp`, which also suppresses some optimisations so that changes to variables from one return are also seen by the second. However, libseff only returns once from a coroutine, so this reduction in optimisation is unnecessary.

2 Pointer Authentication

Pointer authentication [5, §D8.10] places small cryptographic signatures into the most-signification bits of pointer values, which are available for reuse because systems do not require full 64-bit virtual address spaces. These signatures can then be checked by stand-alone instructions or special forms of branch.

The keys used for signing are managed by the operating system, and an additional *diversifier* value (also known as a discriminator or salt) can be provided by the application code to tie the signature to a particular purpose. Checking the codes can therefore detect alterations to signed pointers and some substitution of pointers.

2.1 Compatibility with previous architectures

Using pointer authentication requires agreement about which pointers are signed, the keys used to sign them, and the diversifiers used. Thus widespread use requires an adapted ABI and is not compatible with code compiled without pointer authentication support. In particular, Apple introduced a new *arm64e* ABI for its operating systems [13, 4] which allows widespread use. The LLVM project also support a *pauthtest* ABI for Linux for experimental purposes, which is close to arm64e.

A lighter touch ‘pac-ret’ approach which is often used in Linux systems only signs function return addresses, using the stack pointer as a diversifier to tie them to the current stack frame. The storage of return addresses is essentially an implementation detail, so this is a minor change to the ABI. Like the landing pads above, the specific instructions used for pac-ret are *hints*, so they no-ops on earlier processors, allowing code compiled for pac-ret to be used on them without recompilation. It also allows PAC to be turned off when part of the executable does not support it.

2.2 Adaption

Basic return pointer protection is simple to implement for libmprompt and libseff: an instruction at the entry of each function to add an authentication code to the return pointer (except for their `longjmp` equivalents, which do not return to the caller), one at the end to check and (if successful) remove the code, and a *note* to tell the linker that the code supports PAC. None of this is specific to effect handlers; exactly the same would be required for any assembly code.

There is another extension of pointer authentication that is compatible with existing code — we can add authentication codes to the target instruction address stored in the libmprompt jump buffer and libseff coroutine structure to protect them against modification. As these structures also store the stack pointer, we can continue to use that as the diversifier, and can also use the hint instructions for backwards compatibility. One small complication is that both libraries also refer to the target address in C code, and we need two extra small pieces of assembly to deal with the authentication codes. First, in libmprompt, some target addresses are compared against a whitelist for extra safety and we need a small assembly routine to remove the authentication codes

so that they are not tied to particular stack frames. In libseff, the initial continuation is set up in C and we need to generate the initial PAC for the target address.

We tested the adapted code and confirmed that the authentication codes were present in both the stack frames and the structures using a debugger.

3 Guarded Control Stacks

Guarded Control Stacks (GCS) [5, §D11] are the Arm form of shadow stack support, which maintains an extra separate stack of return addresses that are checked on each return instruction, ensuring well-bracketed control-flow. The virtual memory protection system is used to ensure that they cannot be easily tampered with. Calls and returns transparently update and check the current shadow stack, while ordinary writes are forbidden. Special instructions can pop items off the stack, and may be able to push items, depending on the permissions allowed.

Intel has shadow stacks [11, Ch. 18] as part of the Control Flow Enforcement technology, and the Zicfiss extension provides them for RISC-V.

The Linux kernel provides a common API for enabling shadow stacks and allocating additional shadow stacks for the Intel and Arm schemes [1]. However, changing the currently active shadow stack within a thread must be handled manually.

3.1 Adaption

We first experimented on an Arm Architectural Envelope Model¹ and a demonstration Yocto Linux system produced by Arm². We only adapted libmprompt because libseff requires clang, and this experimental setup only supported GCC. Later, after the adaption work was completed, support for qemu and Linux distributions was added, and we confirmed some details using Debian Linux.

The glibc library had already been adapted to GCS, providing support for `setjmp/longjmp` and the POSIX `ucontext` API, which provided exemplars for the changes required. A plain stack switch takes a few instructions to swap the shadow stack pointer and mark the old stack as inactive, and a couple more to check for GCS and skip the swap when it's not available for compatibility. The jump buffer recorded by `setjmp` is extended to keep the shadow stack pointer for the switch. However, `longjmp`, and its counterpart in libmprompt, may also discard a number of stack frames, and similarly we may need to additionally discard enough entries on the shadow stack to reach the point at which `setjmp` was called.

The other change libmprompt required was the allocation of an extra shadow stack alongside each new stack, using the system call provided by Linux. Shadow stacks can be deallocated using `munmap`, but libmprompt pools the stacks it allocates for fast reuse, so we also reuse the corresponding shadow stacks. However, this does require a little extra startup code when entering a stacklet to pop any old shadow stack entries.

Support for multishot effect handlers is more difficult. These are implemented in libmprompt by duplicating the resumption when necessary, and here that would involve duplicating the shadow stack. We could implement this by enabling direct accesses to the shadow stack, but this would reduce the amount of protection provided. We believe that a better approach would be to add support for duplicating shadow stacks to the Linux API, perhaps using the virtual memory system to provide copy-on-write allocation to reduce overall cost.

4 CHERI hardware capabilities

CHERI is an approach to extending existing instruction set architectures with hardware capabilities to help enforce memory safety and provide fine-grained compartmentalisation [16]. Where

¹'Fast Models 11.25 Base Rev C FVP'

²See <https://youtu.be/VSX1jcPDMic?t=726> for details.

instructions in the base architecture use addresses, the extension uses capabilities that also include metadata about the bounds of the object pointed to and the permitted uses of the capability. Registers and the memory subsystem are extended to handle these larger capabilities, and, crucially, an out-of-band *validity* tag bit for each capability to ensure that they are unforgeable. If an access is made where the pointer is outside the bounds, or without sufficient permissions, then a processor exception will halt execution of the program.

CHERI also provides *sealed* capabilities that further restrict their use, either by requiring a corresponding unsealing capability, or through a restricted form of call, which can be used for compartmentalisation and control-flow integrity.

Capabilities are used for C pointers when targeting CHERI architectures, with the bounds set to the size of the object allocated by default, providing a high degree of *spatial* memory safety. The compiler can also narrow the bounds when pointers are taken to subobjects such as fields of a structure, although this requires more changes to source code, and we do not consider it further here. Compilers use sealed pointers by default for function pointers and internally for return addresses to provide a degree of control flow integrity.

In addition to enforcing spatial safety, CHERI systems often provide *temporal* memory safety in the form of use-after-reallocation protection by quarantining recently freed memory and performing a sweep of memory to clear capabilities to it before reuse [7, 8], albeit with some additional overhead.

These changes to normal compilation represent a major ABI break, although several CHERI platforms support running legacy code in separate processes. For most programs they also require a very small amount of source code adaption, such as reworking illegal pointer arithmetic that happens to work on other platforms. However, code that is closely tied to the language runtime or that features assembly, including our effect handler libraries, usually requires more careful work, as discussed below.

CHERI has been implemented in a range of experimental platforms, in particular the Arm Morello prototype that provided a 4-core system in silicon based on Arm’s Neoverse N1 design. A RISC-V extension is in the standardisation process, and several implementations exist, including open source designs and early commercial products. In particular, the RISC-V based CHERI_{IoT} platform for embedded systems has been realised in SCI Semiconductor’s ICENI microcontrollers.

4.1 Adaption

Part of the adaption cost of CHERI is that the bounds in the metadata have to be compressed to keep capabilities a reasonable size (double the address size). The compression is relative to the current address, so any pointer arithmetic must keep the address close to the bounds at all times, otherwise the compression will fail, the validity tag will be cleared, and the capability will be unusable.

Core to adapting libmprompt and libseff was to add a new version of the stack switching assembly code, in particular copying the larger capability registers in and out of memory, and updating the extra debug information necessary for a debugger to understand the stack switch to match the new memory layout. An alignment calculation in libmprompt had to be changed to use the new `alignd` instruction because the logical and instruction used before is not suitable for capabilities.

The changes required for libmprompt’s C code are typical for a CHERI porting exercise: some data structures that assumed 64-bit pointers were changed to use `intptr_t`; some pointer alignment calculations used division and multiplication, which is incompatible with bounds compression, so were replaced by calculating the offset then adjusting the capability; and a C programming idiom to add data to the end of a `struct` had to be adjusted to align the data sufficiently so that a capability can be stored there.

A more unusual feature of libmprompt is the use of *guard cookies* — where the stored instruction and stack addresses in a resumption are protected by xor encoding with a randomly chosen guard cookie. Again, this is incompatible with bounds compression, so we turned the feature off and rely on the memory protection provided by CHERI instead. However, it would also be

possible to provide a similar form of protection using capability sealing, where a sealing capability acts as the guard cookie.

This is sufficient to run libmprompt programs, but there is a further improvement to match the general behaviour expected in CHERI C, that capability bounds are limited to the allocated memory. There is a custom allocator for stacklet address space in the library, and we added a little code to shrink the capability bounds returned to the stacklet’s allocation rather than the entire region reserved for stacklets. This provides protection from stack overflows, and we could even drop the guard pages previously used for partial overflow protection.

In a low level language like C, the support for multi-shot effect handlers leaves us exposed to resource handling errors, such as use-after-free mistakes from resuming the computation after an effect multiple times. Indeed, CHERI’s temporal safety support allows us to demonstrate this: we constructed a small sample program that performs an effect, uses some preallocated memory and frees it, and a handler for the effect which resumes multiple times, and showed that when set to sweep aggressively the program will fault at the memory access in the second run. However, when the sweeping is set to normal we see the difference between use-after-free protection and use-after-reallocation protection - the memory is still in quarantine at the second use, so the access is successful and the program continues.

The adaption of libseff has similar assembly requirements to libmprompt, as well as a script that produces C and assembly declarations for the target architecture that had to be updated to reflect additional struct alignment constraints and to distinguish pointer types from word types, which are different on CHERI.

We also experimented with two other effect handler implementations on CHERI. The cpeffects library [10] provides a C++ implementation, using the boost-context library to provide stack switching. We adapted boost-context’s fcontext back-end with similar changes to the assembly in libmprompt and libseff, adjusting sizes and offsets of data and changing an alignment instruction. The main cpeffects library required no additional changes.

The second was Koka, a functional language with effects whose compiler uses C code as an intermediate language. The compiler itself is written in Haskell and we did not have a suitable Arm version of Haskell for the version of BSD available. Instead, we cross-compiled sample programs, using the Morello toolchain on the intermediate C code to produce executables. The C code uses explicit data structures for control flow [18], so there was no assembly code to adapt. The main issue encountered with the koka runtime library was the use of the lower bits of values as flags about the contents; function pointers are represented by sealed capabilities to protect control flow and any manipulation of their value to change flags will invalidate the capability. Fortunately, we can use the fact that function pointers are valid code capabilities to detect them, and only use the flags for other data types. More routine changes included changing some types to be large enough for capabilities and fixing a `struct` size calculation that didn’t include padding.

4.2 Compartmentalisation

A linker-based compartmentalisation model for CheriBSD is under development [9] which roughly separates each process into compartments based on shared libraries, applying an external policy to control accesses between compartments. It uses a separate trusted stack and ‘trampoline’ functions to manage transitions between compartments, and provides functional support for inter-compartment `setjmp/longjmp` and C++ exceptions with stack unwinding functions, although the security implications of these features has not yet been explored.

We hypothesise that the main work required to adapt a low-level effect library to this scheme would be to add split trusted stacks to complement the regular stacklets that are used for effect handlers. Some care might also be required if multi-shot handlers were to be supported because resuming a suspended computation multiple times from outside a compartment could easily break assumptions in the compartmentalisation scheme.

5 Other architectural extensions

Memory tagging extensions such as Arm’s MTE [5, §D.10] provide some probabilistic memory protection by adding additional tag memory for each small chunk of memory (4 bits for every 16 bytes in MTE) and to the top bits of pointers and checking they match whenever a pointer is used. (There is a trade-off with pointer authentication over how many bits of a pointer are allocated to each extension.) When there is a tag mismatch, for example due to an out-of-bounds access or a stale pointers, there will be a processor exception to signal a memory error. We tested libprompt under qemu’s Arm emulation and glibc’s support for allocating random tags to `malloc` allocations. The tests ran successfully with no changes and we were able to confirm that tagging was active using a debugger. One possible extension would be to also apply random tags when allocating stacklets to prevent the use of stale pointers to old stacklets.

Arm have also announced an extension to their permissions overlay feature, POE2 [17], where the permissions used for pages of memory can vary depending on the program counter and an index system register, essentially providing a compartmentalisation primitive for applications to use. As with MTE this largely affects heap allocations and is not expected to cause any immediate implementation problems for effect handlers, although it might be possible to use effect handlers as a compartment boundary. The related Thread-Private State (TPS) extension could be used alongside POE2 to restrict the portion of stack accessible at any point, although this would not be compatible with C code that passes pointers to stack objects between compartments.

6 Discussion

The experience of adapting these libraries was greatly aided by the most similar parts of the standard library. Support for `setjmp` and `longjmp` is essentially universal, and the need for new features to interoperate with C means that skipping stack frames and returning twice from a function are supported to some extent. More surprisingly, the obsolete (and now removed) POSIX `get/set/swapcontext` interface [14] is still widely supported in Linux and BSD systems and encourages architects to design new features to be compatible with stack switching. We hypothesise that the increasing popularity of coroutines will have a similar effect.

However, the existing support in toolchains can be overspecialised. For example, the compiler attributes used to ensure that landing pads appear for Branch Target Identification in Section 1.1 are not standardised, and the only available choice for clang also has other side-effects. There may also be differences in performance expectations that have an impact on the implementation choices; for example, it would be reasonable to assume that `longjmp` is used sparingly, whereas we would expect to be able to use an effect handler frequently.

Multi-shot effect handlers, as found in libprompt, are less like traditional C control flow and thus can require more work. This was particularly true for Guarded Control Stacks where Linux does not currently support stack copying, and we would expect CHERI compartmentalisation would also require careful thought.

A common theme in pointer authentication, CHERI, and memory tagging are to add more structure to pointers, often violating the expectations of legacy C code when they need to go beyond standard ISO C. The comparison of code pointers with a whitelist in Section 2.2 for pointer authentication is a good example of this. CHERI capabilities take this a step further because well-intentioned changes to an address can break the compression or sealing schemes, both of which we saw in libprompt. Using CHERI capabilities also presents many of the porting issues you normally see when moving to a completely different architecture, especially due to the increased alignment constraints.

7 Further work

We have primarily sought compatibility with new ISA features here, in order to avoid completely losing the protection offered by them, and an obvious next step would be to assess the impact of

these effect handler implementations on that protection and whether there are opportunities to improve it. For example, in Section 2.2 we added pointer authentication codes to the instruction pointer in each jump buffer — this was not strictly necessary, but we hope that it would detect corruption of the instruction pointer and hence increase safety.

Similarly, the CHERI ISA extension provides several avenues for further investigation, many of which would use the *sealed capabilities* feature’s additional anti-tamper protection. Section 4.1 mentioned that sealed capabilities might be able to provide similar protection to the guard cookies that had to be disabled, and Section 4.2 summarised how our effect handler libraries could be adapted to linker-based compartmentalisation. The latter should be accompanied by an analysis of whether internal details of a compartment could be leaked through effects and how any leaks could be prevented. Moreover, we hypothesise that handlers might form a good compartment boundary, especially if direct access to system calls is forbidden, because the handlers could track state changes and so potentially recover from a failure inside the compartment by rolling them back.

Beyond the linker-based compartments, the CHERI_{IoT} RTOS system [3] uses compartments in a single address-space to provide a fine-grained alternative to processes. At present it provides limited stack unwinding for errors crossing between compartments, not even supporting C++ exceptions, so it would be an interesting target for low-level effect handlers, and could provide additional insights over the linker-based scheme.

The pointer authentication work could also be extended to cover more a extensive ABI such as Apple’s arm64e and the Linux pauthtest. No major obstacles are expected, but there might be opportunities for strengthening the protection, similar to adding codes to the instruction pointers in jump buffers mentioned above.

Finally, we should study the performance implications of these adapted effect handler implementations. This is not entirely easy when using simulation because it may not reflect real hardware behaviour (not to mention the wide variations between different processor cores), or when using prototype hardware like Morello, where optimising the processor to normal production quality was beyond the scope of the project and assessing performance is difficult [15]. There are signs that there may be important performance impacts; for example, glibc’s `longjmp` source code has a comment that using a `ret` instruction rather than a branch will cause a misprediction. We would expect the non-local control flow in effect handler implementations to face similar issues, especially as modern processors maintain caches of return addresses for prediction. It might be possible to provide hints beyond instruction choice to improve prediction, and it would be interesting to see if shadow stack support like the GCS extension in Section 3 is generally used for prediction, in which case supporting it would improve performance.

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